

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

Reference: 101087984

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

National Report

[Velenje, Slovenia]

WP2 D2.1

[Andragoški zavod Ljudska univerza Velenje]

Amendment History

Version	Revision	Date	Avthor	Modification
1	0	26.9.2023	Mihaela Orozel	Final version

Table of content

1.	INTRODUCTION	4
2.	GENDER EQUALITY AND GENDER REPRESENTATION IN SLOVENIA.....	4
3.	GENDER REPRESENTATION IN HISTORY IN SLOVENIA.....	5
4.	GENDER REPRESENTATION IN HISTORY IN VELENJE	7
5.	FEMALE FOOTPRINT IN VELENJE AND SAVINJSKO-ŠALEŠKA REGION	7
6.	CITY'S PRACTICES IN DISSEMINATING GENDER BALANCED HISTORY	9
6.1.	LOCAL STRATEGIES	9
7.	FOCUS GROUPS WITH YOUNG PEOPLE: ANALYSES AND RESULTS	10
7.1.	FINDINGS ON "LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE IN HISTORY"	10
7.2.	FINDINGS ON TOPIC "FEMALE FIGURES AND MALE FIGURES THROUGHOUT THE HISTORY"	10
7.3.	FINDINGS ON "METHODS TO PROMOTE WOMEN'S FOOTPRINT IN HISTORY"	11
8.	FOCUS GROUP WITH STAKEHOLDERS: ANALYSES AND RESULTS	12
8.1.	FINDINGS ON "RELEVANCE WITH THE FIELD OF HISTORY"	12
8.2.	FINDINGS ON "HISTORY THROUGH THE LENS OF THEIR EXPERTISE"	12
8.3.	FINDINGS ON "EXPERIENCE WITH YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE FIELD OF HISTORY"	13
8.4.	FINDINGS ON "WOMEN'S FOOTPRINT IN HISTORY"	13
9.	CONCLUSIONS.....	15

1. Introduction

The project HerStory aims to change the narrative that the field of history is a male dominant field. History focuses on the value of men's contribution to history and their role in shaping society. HerStory project will fill the lack of information about women's presence and contribution in history. As the mainstream literature on women's history is limited, their contribution to society and their struggles are more likely invisible.

HerStory project through a bottom-up research approach will raise the visibility of women in history. Through the development of local multi-stakeholder networks, the consortium will challenge the field of history in a gender perspective way. During this research the consortium will detect statues and historical areas that represent female figures in history and will raise the knowledge towards this information.

The aim of the desk research "Mapping the women footprint on local histories" is to investigate women's triumphs and normalise the success of women through the publicity of women statues and monuments, street names, historical places related to women presence in the society. In this way any historical misconceptions and misrepresentation can be addressed towards gender equality.

The desk research is important in order to fill the gap of missing information regarding women's footprint in history. The results from the desk research will contribute to change the frame and the reflection of conclusive male patterns impact on people. The outcomes of the research will provide knowledge and inspiration to young people and stakeholders. Finally, the results of the desk research will work as a source of information for the development of the transnational map where the visitors will be able to find remarkable places regarding women in history in all partner's cities of the consortium.

2. Gender equality and gender representation in Slovenia

The Slovenian Constitution ensures equal human rights and freedoms, prohibiting discrimination based on personal circumstances, including sex. It also guarantees the right to equal job opportunities. Gender mainstreaming, introduced in 2002 through the Equal Opportunities for Women and Men Act, is a key legal tool for gender equality. The first national program on gender equality was adopted in 2005, making gender mainstreaming a cross-cutting strategy. The latest strategy, the National Programme for Equal Opportunities 2015–2020, employs both special measures and gender mainstreaming to advance practical gender equality across policies and programs.

Nonetheless, structural constraints in Slovenia impact gender equality across various aspects, including economic participation, leadership representation, work-life balance, education, legal frameworks, cultural norms, and healthcare access. These constraints contribute to issues like the gender wage gap, underrepresentation of women in leadership roles, and challenges in balancing work and personal life. Addressing these structural barriers is vital for advancing gender equality in Slovenia and requires a comprehensive approach involving government policies, societal shifts, and initiatives from multiple sectors.

It is important to realise that women's equality needs to be seen from several perspectives. Not only in law, but also in practice. They must have equal social power, equal representation in the spheres of public and private life and the same benefits of advancement. Equality is by no means the same thing, however, and it is therefore also necessary to look at the differences between the sexes. Slovenia has therefore drawn up a national plan for the implementation of the programme for equal opportunities for women and men, in which it has identified eight areas: equal economic independence, reconciliation of private and professional life, a knowledge society free of gender stereotypes, social inclusion, women's and men's health, balanced representation of women and men in decision-making positions, violence against women, and gender equality in foreign policy and international development cooperation.

Slovenia applies gender mainstreaming to the implementation of its strategic plans, which in practice means that for every policy, measure or criterion that is planned, we have to examine what impact and consequences it would have on women and men. The Law on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men stipulates that all ministries must appoint a coordinator or focal point to ensure that a gender perspective is integrated into measures and policies. In addition to the government and ministries, local self-governing authorities are also committed to promoting and creating equal opportunities. To facilitate these tasks, the law allows municipalities to appoint a coordinator. This shows that women have also started to make their mark in the natural sciences and technical professions and, surprisingly, the proportion of women in the IT and cyber security sectors has risen sharply. By including women in leadership positions, Slovenia is enforcing quotas and the inclusion of the female gender in top positions.

3. Gender representation in history in Slovenia

The role of gender representation in history is an important aspect of promoting gender equality. Historically, women have been underrepresented in the field of history, both as subjects of historical research and as historians themselves. This has resulted in a lack of attention to women's experiences and contributions in historical narratives.

The available data underscores the underrepresentation of women in Slovenia, an imbalance historically influenced by significant male involvement, as well as prevailing political structures. Presently, men continue to dominate the narrative of what is commonly referred to as "visible history." Nonetheless, empirical evidence indicates that the majority of women actively contribute to the co-creation and advancement of various programs. Consequently, historical records substantiate that women played pivotal roles in formulating educational frameworks, instrumental in propelling Slovenia to its status as one of the most educationally advanced nations worldwide. Additionally, it is evident that women have traditionally spearheaded research endeavours, particularly within the medical domain, as well as fostered cultural and artistic expressions.

In response to this, Slovenia has introduced a curriculum component within primary education, dedicated to spotlighting Slovenian women who have indelibly shaped the course of history. Rozalia Sršen (1897-1967), widely regarded as Slovenia's preeminent actress, transitioned from a prominent Hollywood career to the metalworking industry,

rendering her one of the most intriguing Slovenian women in historical retrospect. Likewise, Alma Maksimiljana Karlin, a distinguished researcher, author, and theosophist hailing from Celje, staunchly resisted the Nazi regime and produced over twenty literary works during her lifetime, including a highly circulated travelogue exceeding 100,000 copies in print. Owing to her exceptional literary acumen, Karlin garnered informal consideration for the Nobel Prize from Swedish circles. The curriculum further encompasses Sophie Hess, Alfred Nobel's confidante, who fabricated a compelling narrative to elicit compassion, support, and financial backing for her cause. This endeavour culminated in the establishment of a Nobel statue in Celje. Additionally, Gizela Štrukel, an inaugural graduate of Jože Plečnik and one of Slovenia's pioneering architects, distinguished herself by crafting aesthetically captivating urban residences. Presently, Štrukel stands as a luminary in Slovenian architectural discourse and the design of commemorative monuments and sepulchers. In the realm of pharmacy, Emilija Fon stands as a trailblazer, being among the earliest women to establish her independent apothecary.

Upon retrospection, Slovenian history bears witness to a multitude of women who have etched their legacies onto the terrain of Slovenia. Figures such as Barbara Celjska, Adelma Von Vay, and Anna Schauberg, among others, have played pivotal roles in shaping Slovenia's historical narrative.

In recent years, there has been a growing awareness of the importance of including women's voices and perspectives in the study of history in Slovenia. Efforts have been made to promote research on women's history and to increase the visibility of women in historical narratives. For example, the Slovenian Women's History Network was established in 2004 to promote research on women's history and to encourage the inclusion of women in historical narratives.

There have also been efforts to increase the representation of women in the field of history itself. While women make up a majority of history students in Slovenia, they are underrepresented in academic and research positions. Efforts have been made to address this issue by promoting gender equality in academic and research institutions, including initiatives to increase the number of women in leadership positions and to address gender bias in academic hiring and promotion processes.

4. Gender representation in history in Velenje

The research and focus groups both show the importance of recognizing and highlighting the often-overlooked contributions of women in local history. In focus groups, participants shed light on various facets of gender equality and women's roles, noting challenges in researching women's history due to a lack of documentation and historical narratives. They also pointed out the glaring underrepresentation of women in street names in Velenje, a city with 102 streets named after figures from the National Liberation War period and artists, but none after women. Efforts have been made to rectify this, with proposals for female street names being submitted. Alma Karlin, a notable polyglot, and traveller from Celje, was cited as an example of a successful promotion of a female figure in history. The conversation also touched on the significant role of mining women in Velenje's history, with participants advocating for statues or exhibits to honour their contributions. During the focus group with young people, it became evident that young people in the Šaleška dolina region have limited knowledge of local history, particularly regarding influential women. They are familiar with Alma M. Karlin's legacy, but unaware of other women who have made substantial contributions to their communities. The discussion grapples with defining exceptional individuals, highlighting that women have historically been excluded from this category due to patriarchal norms. The participants express a keen interest in understanding the roles of "miner's wives" and "female partisans," as well as the broader contributions of women in post-war reconstruction and the development of Velenje. There is an evident need to acknowledge and celebrate the multifaceted roles of women in history, while also recognizing the challenges and biases that have historically marginalized their contributions.

5. Female footprint in Velenje and Savinjsko-Šaleška region

During the desk research and focus groups the following female figures were identified.

In Velenje:

Jelka Reichman (1926-2017) was a Slovenian painter and illustrator who was born in Velenje. She is best known for her illustrations for children's books, many of which have become classics of Slovenian children's literature.

Zofka Kveder (1878-1926) was a writer and feminist who was born in Velenje. She was a pioneer of Slovenian feminist literature and was known for her novels, short stories, and essays.

Ljudmila Novak (born 1959) is a Slovenian politician who served as the mayor of Velenje from 1994 to 1998. She is also a former member of the Slovenian Parliament and served as the president of the Slovenian Democratic Party from 2000 to 2013.

Herma Groznik (1940-2022) Herma has been very active in shaping the local community throughout her life. She was a teacher who loved to be involved in many activities, but she had a special love for scouting and her contribution in this field was really great. Many would agree that it is to her credit that Scouting has become a part of all the primary schools in Velenje.

In 2005, Hermina Groznik received a high municipal award - the coat of arms of the Municipality of Velenje - for her significant contribution to the local community.

Antonija Strnad (1873–1950) – midwife, helped to deliver around 4.000 babies during her professional life.

A miner's wife – fictional role.

In Celje:

Alma Karlin (1889-1950) was a Slovenian writer, traveller, and polyglot who was born in Celje. She travelled extensively throughout the world and wrote several books about her experiences, including "Globetrotting Through Siberia and Central Asia" and "In the Land of Silent People".

Franja Bojc Bidovec (1913-1944) was a Slovenian nurse who worked in a secret hospital in the mountains near Celje during World War II. She helped to care for wounded Partisan fighters and saved the lives of many people despite the constant threat of discovery and capture by the occupying forces.

Lili Novy (1885-1958) was a Slovenian poet, translator, and feminist who was born in Celje. She was a leading figure in Slovenian feminist literature and was known for her poems, essays, and translations of works by other writers.

These women, both known and lesser known, have left their mark in different areas of interest in Velenje and Celje, contributing to the cultural and intellectual heritage of their respective cities and the wider Slovenian society.

6. City's practices in disseminating gender balanced history

The practices in disseminating gender balanced history are very limited. The initiative to disseminate a gender-balanced history is informed by the challenges in researching and acknowledging women's historical contributions, stemming from a lack of documentation and narratives. The stark underrepresentation of women in the city's street names has been one of the concerns, prompting efforts to propose female names.

There is a need to emphasize the pivotal role of women, particularly mining women, in Velenje's history, advocating for the acknowledgment and celebration of their contributions. Addressing the historical gender bias is crucial, and educational initiatives should be implemented to bridge the knowledge gap, ensuring that the stories of both men and women are equally celebrated and remembered in Velenje's historical narrative.

6.1. Local strategies

In Velenje, the city has a strong focus on promoting the history of the city and its industrial heritage. The city's practices in disseminating history patterns include the Velenje Museum, which showcases the history of the city and its mining industry, and the Velenje Castle, which houses a museum of local history. The city also hosts regular cultural and historical events, including the Velenje Festival, which features a range of cultural and artistic events, and the Festival of Industrial Heritage, which celebrates the city's industrial past.

The neighbouring city Celje has a more diverse approach to disseminating history patterns. While the city also has a strong focus on promoting its history, it also emphasizes the importance of cultural heritage and art. The city's practices in disseminating history patterns include the Celje Regional Museum, which showcases the history of the city and the wider region, and the Celje Gallery of Contemporary Art, which features exhibitions of contemporary art. The city also hosts regular cultural events, including the Celje International Children's Festival and the Days of Poetry and Wine, which celebrate poetry and wine from the region.

If women were previously neglected when depicting the important milestones in the town's history, that is not the case at present. In Velenje, there are several women who have been awarded a plaque by the municipality of Velenje for their contribution to improving the lives of the citizens. For example, the Curator of the Year, who tried to introduce artistic culture to Velenje, the Scout woman, who developed the mentality of scouting in Velenje, the politicians who have been ministers, and of course many sportswomen. Every year Velenje also hosts the largest children's festival, dedicated to a girl (albeit fictitious) called "Pikin festival" (Pippi Långstrump), which emphasises that women are capable of anything they desire.

7. Focus groups with young people: Analyses and results

Two focus groups took place. The first focus group included students from technical and grammar schools, with a casual interest in history. They held firm opinions on the discussion topic, and one participant even hailed from the University of Ljubljana. The second focus group gathered students from various vocational and secondary schools, showcasing varying levels of interest in history. Among them was a participant who had previously conducted research on the perceptions of women across different age groups in the Upper Savinja Valley, examining social roles, gender equality, and how lifestyles evolve over generations.

7.1. Findings on “Level of knowledge in history”

Participants in the discussion emphasized the interconnectedness of all events with history, viewing current happenings as part of the past. They identified their knowledge of history as primarily influenced by their teachers' varying approaches in both primary and secondary school, as well as their personal interest in historical events. Regarding the teaching of history in schools, they believed that educators often focus on facts aligned with the current ruling ideology. They expressed a preference for delving into the research aspect of history rather than concentrating solely on historically significant figures for economic and social relations of current authorities. Participants felt that military and political power receive undue emphasis, while the individual histories are overlooked. The group identified several reasons for young people's disinterest in history, including a lack of societal engagement, self-centered behavior, and a diminished sense of collective belonging. Economic concerns, particularly career-building, were also cited. They suggested that employing modern teaching methods, similar to those in Denmark, could significantly heighten interest in history. Additionally, it became evident that young people possess limited knowledge of local history, particularly regarding influential women, except for Alma M. Karlin, a world traveler, writer, and poet who left her mark on the Celje area. Some participants had visited an exhibition about her life, but they were generally unfamiliar with other significant women in their local community.

7.2. Findings on topic “Female figures and male figures throughout the history”

In the discussion about notable women in history, participants note the scarcity of well-known female figures, attributing this to historical gender biases where men were celebrated as warriors and leaders while women were often marginalized. They highlight the progress made in women's rights, particularly gaining the right to vote after 1945. Reasons for women's historical underrepresentation include religious beliefs, biased teachings in schools, and deliberate suppression of outspoken women, often labelled as witches.

Some women, however, worked behind the scenes to support male achievers. The conversation underscores the evolving role of women over time and acknowledges gaps in our understanding of their historical contributions. They recognize the prevalence of male figures in historical recognition, largely due to patriarchal inheritance practices.

Determining criteria for outstanding female figures is deemed challenging due to limited historical opportunities. The group expresses interest in exploring the roles of "miner's wives" and "female partisans," shedding light on women's contributions in the mining industry and their involvement during World War II. They also express curiosity about women's role in post-war reconstruction and the particular impact of women in Velenje's socialist post-war period.

7.3. Findings on “Methods to promote women’s footprint in history”

Methods that some of the participants have already encountered and feel would help to present history in an interesting and engaging way to young people are:

- role-playing in the school history subject
- short films about historical events
- telling stories of people who experienced the events through their own experiences
- stories through art (paintings, graffiti, etc.)
- virtual visits to exhibitions, simulations of events, etc.

When discussing the methods our participants would use to promote women who have left their mark on Slovenian history, they mainly referred to the use of mobile phone apps. It refers mainly to apps:

- Google Maps - we would add an icon:
- Landmarks / or outstanding female personalities and a short description or link to a website or short film showing the life and work of the personality,
- A mobile app (such as Pokemon GO) that can be used by different age groups, where you collect points when you visit each landmark and when you collect them all, you get a symbolic prize.

Their suggestions on how to inspire young people and introduce them to history are mainly along the following lines:

- the need to change the way education is delivered
- organise events - readings – discussions;
- it is important to encourage research among young people;
- the project "Youth for the Development of the Šaleška Valley" was highlighted, which enables young people to present their projects in public;
- young people need to be made aware that history is not over, it is still going on and that we are all making and writing it.

How they see the herstory map tells us:

- ➔ Google Maps / Route (guided or self-guided) with a selection of important landmarks as well as important women in the environment (but it is important that there is a café in between to give you a break - similar to "Pozoj's Castle Route", or "Experience Socialism in Velenje on Youth Day").

They also mentioned that a lot of work needs to be done on content to attract young people back to the city.

8. Focus group with stakeholders: Analyses and results

8.1. Findings on "Relevance with the field of History"

The participants in the project represented a diverse array of roles closely tied to the field of history and cultural heritage. These roles encompassed individuals actively engaged in various aspects of historical preservation, education, research, and museum management. Among the participants were employees of Villa Mayer, specialists focused on preserving and popularizing cultural heritage. Others had experience in teaching at the Technical School and Gymnasium, contributing directly to historical education. Additionally, there were historians and curators at Velenje Museum, responsible for documentation, museum collections management, and historical research. Furthermore, a librarian from the Velenje Library brought expertise in history and sociology of culture to the discussion, while a representative from the Velenje Tourist Board, a significant entity in tourism, represented the tourist sector. This diverse and multifaceted assembly of roles collectively enhances the project's exploration of history and its multifaceted significance.

8.2. Findings on "History through the lens of their expertise"

Participants in this conversation, experts in gender equality and women's historical roles, focused on the challenges of researching and documenting women's history, along with historical perceptions of feminism and women's unique expressions of power. They highlighted the difficulty in finding information about women's contributions due to their often private and less-documented roles compared to men in more public positions. Additionally, participants discussed specific historical periods, such as miners' widows facing significant challenges. They noted the context of feminism being viewed unfavorably under socialism and the impact of positive discrimination, particularly in the Soviet Union. The participants also recognized women's adaptability and excellence across various fields, often referred to as "multipractitioners." They highlighted a strong female presence in the tourism sector, where women hold significant leadership roles and drive progress. Overall, the discussion illuminated the evolving narrative of women's historical roles and the persistent challenges in uncovering their contributions.

8.3. Findings on “Experience with young people in the field of History”

The participants in this discussion are experienced in working with young people in the field of history, acting as mentors and guides, offering valuable advice and support to budding historians. They have been actively involved in educational outreach at academic institutions, demonstrating a commitment to sharing historical expertise with students, particularly in the domain of gender and women's history. The feedback on young people's engagement with history is mixed. While there's recognition of the prevalence of digital distractions, there's also an acknowledgment of opportunities to educate them about historical and gender-related topics through innovative approaches. The participants note that young people are attuned to modern trends, especially in terms of gender definitions influenced by social networks. They emphasize efforts to make history more engaging for the youth, mentioning initiatives like the Young Museum and educational programs. However, there's concern about a potential gap in presenting everyday life and local history in schools, making it less relatable to students.

Stakeholders propose creating resources like maps highlighting exceptional women in history to make the subject more appealing. The main reasons cited for the lack of interest in history among young people include:

digital distractions,

a perception of history as less engaging,

gender disparities in curriculum representation, and

a need for innovative educational tools.

The participants suggest various interactive and immersive learning methods, such as role-playing, multimedia presentations, and collaborative learning, to make history a dynamic and engaging subject for the youth. They also emphasize the importance of presenting history as a living, evolving narrative rather than static facts.

8.4. Findings on “Women’s footprint in History”

In this discussion, the participants shed light on several facets of gender equality and women's roles in history. They mention the challenges faced in researching women's history, emphasizing the lack of documentation and historical narratives regarding women, especially those in the private sphere. They discuss the historical roles of women in various contexts, including their contributions to society, politics, and the workplace.

The participants highlighted the underrepresentation of women in Velenje's street names.

Velenje has 102 streets named after people from the NOB (National Liberation War) period and artists, but none are named after women. Participants discussed the absence of female names on streets and suggested that efforts have been made to change this, with proposals for female street names being submitted.

Additionally, they mentioned Alma Karlin, a notable woman from Celje, as an example of a successful promotion of a female figure in history. Alma Karlin was a polyglot and traveller, and her contributions to history have gained recognition. The conversation also touched on the role of mining women in Velenje's history and their significant contributions.

Participants expressed the need to acknowledge and celebrate the roles of women in history, including miners' wives, and proposed the idea of dedicating statues or exhibits to women's contributions in the mining industry. Finally, the text mentioned ongoing collaborations and projects related to women's history, particularly focusing on the centenary of a woman's birth.

9. Conclusions

The HerStory project has undertaken a vital mission in reshaping the historical narrative, specifically targeting the prevailing male dominance in the field of history. By focusing on women's contributions and presence in history, HerStory aims to bridge the information gap surrounding women's impact on society, often obscured in mainstream literature.

Through desk research and focus groups, the project gathered significant insights. It became evident that while strides have been made in legislation and policy frameworks for gender equality in Slovenia, structural impediments persist, impacting various facets of life, including economic participation, leadership representation, and work-life balance.

In the field of education, participants acknowledged the challenges in raising interest in history among young people, who are increasingly immersed in digital distractions. However, they also emphasized the potential for innovative approaches, such as role-playing, multimedia presentations, and collaborative learning, to make history more dynamic and engaging.

Furthermore, the project's exploration of gender representation in history, both in Slovenia and specifically in Velenje, highlighted the historical biases that have marginalized women's contributions. Efforts to rectify this imbalance, including proposing female street names and commemorating minor's wife as a female representative of important part of history.

The HerStory project aims to illuminate the diverse roles of women in history, shedding light on their invaluable contributions across various domains. By developing a platform to celebrate and remember these remarkable individuals, the project has taken a significant step towards rewriting history as an inclusive and living narrative. This will ensure that women's impact on history keeps on inspiring and influencing how society thinks and feels together.